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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, Higher education is believed to be the major avenue for national development but its accessibility and effectiveness are increasingly questionable by economic challenges. By implication, this study investigates the influence of financial constraint on student academic performance with particular reference to Federal Polytechnic Ayede and The Polytechnic Ibadan. Hence, two specific objectives were considered which include to find out the extent to which financial constraint will affect the academic performance of students and examine how the socio-economic status of the parent in determining the academic performance of students. Descriptive survey research design was employed; self-designed questionnaire and executive interview guide were used to obtain data from the respondent. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select one hundred fifty (150) respondents among the government owned Polytechnic in Oyo state (The Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede). Both descriptive and new generation inferential statistical were employed to perform the data analysis. specifically, the study findings confirmed that parent job status, father education, mother education, financial constraint, recreational activities, house ownership, income and parent job significantly predicted academic performance of Federal Polytechnic Ayede Students [(R² = .380; F (7,74) = 5.060; p < .01)] while parent job status, father education, mother education, financial constraint, recreational activities, house ownership and income significantly predicted academic performance of the Polytechnic Ibadan students[(R² = .259; F (7, 74) = 3.342; p < .004)]. The empirical outcomes revealed that there exist a significant inverse relationship between financial constraint and the academic performance, it was also confirmed that the socio-economic status of the parent is significant in determining the academic performance of students. The study recommended that government and private sectors should make adequate provisions for more scholarships especially for indigent students whose parents cannot afford to send them to higher institution of learning, among others, parents should provide all support (financial, moral emotional) to their children irrespective of gender.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Financial Constraint, Socio-economic status

Introduction

The concept of academic performance has become a source of concern to researchers, especially as the academic performance of the undergraduates becomes sparingly challenging. Academic performance is defined as participants' examination grades (Grade point average) at the end of a particular semester or programme (Egbule, 2024). Student academic performance refers to the level of achievement a student attains in their educational pursuits, commonly measured through grades, test scores, and engagement in learning activities. According to Tinto (2017), academic performance is closely linked to student retention, persistence, and the ability to integrate into the educational environment. However, evidences revealed that students' academic performance in schools, (tertiary institutions in particular) has declined considerably over time (Egbule, 2014; Ugoji, 2018). According to the Joint Admissions and

Matriculation Board (JAMB) report (2023), the average tuition in Federal universities rose by over 50% between 2020 and 2023, despite no significant increase in government scholarships. Many students now rely on irregular remittances from parents or seek part-time work to pay their fees. This often results in fatigue, divided attention which affects their academic performance. This could be because they are confronted with so many school and non-school related demands and responsibilities. This problem seems to be a major one that requires urgent and serious solution since students' academic performance affects the quality of human resources within the society (Ebenuwa-Okoh, 2010). Many parents are left with great distress as a result of their children not performing as expected in the university, by implication, many students either abandon their studies or are been sent out of school due to their inability to catch up and cope with the pace of the degree of academic excellence required of them; this is perceived to be traced to financial constraint and socioeconomic status of the parent.

Research Questions

- i. What is the extent to which financial constraint will affect the academic performance of students of The Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede.
- ii. What is the extent to which the socio-economic status of the parent in determining the academic performance of students of The Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede.

Objectives of the Study

The study's broad aim is to examine the In general, the aim of this research is to empirically examine the effect of financial constraint on the academic performance of The Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede, Oyo state Nigeria. To achieve the study's main aim, the following specific objectives have been formulated.

- i. to find out the extent to which financial constraint will affect the academic performance of students of The Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede.
- ii. examine how the socio-economic status of the parent in determining the academic performance of students of The Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nigerian students are exposed to several problems which make it difficult for them to attain good performances and capable of bringing about sustainable development in future. Apart from the federal government inadequate funding in education, low quality and high cost of schooling, there are many problems encountered by universities students and these problems pose negative implication on their academic performance. The effects of these problems on the academic performance of students have negative outcome on the education standard in Nigeria. (Abiona, Fakoya, & Adeogun, 2014). Different problems posed threat to student's academic performance. Problems such as time management, too much involvement in social activities, financial problem, sleep donations, emotional problems, involvement in part time job, can affect students' academic performance. Many studied have identified study habit, student's self-concept, lecturers' qualification, lecturing method, school environment and government factors influencing student's academic performance (Ebenuwa-Okoh, 2010). Besides other factors, socio-economic status is one of the most researched and debated factor among educational professionals that contribute towards the academic performance of students. The most prevalent argument is that the socio-economic status of learners affects the quality of their academic performance. Most of the experts argue that the low socio-economic status has negative effect on the academic performance of students because the basic needs of students remain unfulfilled and hence they do not perform better academically (Musarat, Sundus, Faqiha, Fozia, & Ayesha, 2018).

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was employed. Self-designed questionnaire and executive interview guide was used to obtain data from the respondents. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select one-hundred and fifty respondents among the government owned Polytechnic in Oyo state (The Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede both located in Oyo state). Questionnaire and structured interview was considered as data collection instruments. In a bid to have a robust and accurate result, both descriptive and new generation inferential statistical tools was employed to

perform the data analysis. The descriptive survey design was employed in this study. The descriptive survey design only entails the researcher to carefully collect data from subjects as it is been treated in their natural setting and analyse such data in order to arrive at some reasonable conclusions (Horowitz, 2003). Furthermore, this research design was adopted because it facilitates gathering a large amount of data quickly within the limited time available to the researcher.

Population

The target population of this study captured both students of students of the Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede. Oyo State, Nigeria. The final participants of this study are one hundred and fifty (150) undergraduate students.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Stratified sampling technique was used to select 150 undergraduate students from both the Polytechnic Ibadan and Federal Polytechnic Ayede while simple random technique was employed in administering the questionnaire. This is due to the nature and work routine of the samples under study. The study sample involved 75 respondents for Federal Polytechnic Ayede students, and 75 respondents for the Polytechnic Ibadan students, and they are all active students of their respective departments.

Model Specification

In order to capture the effects of financial constraint on the academic performance of the students, we specify a model in line with the above theoretical framework. In our study, we adopt the finance constraint model, which states that performance (both industrial and academic) depends on finances (financial structure) and some control variables. We modify the finance constraint model by augmenting it with socio-economic variables to adequately capture students' academic performance. Below is the model adapted for the study;

$$Q = AK^{\alpha}L^{\beta}$$

Q= Quantity of output

K= Quantity of Capital input

L= Quantity of Labour input

A= Productivity constant

The model above was adapted from Production function in Producer theory by Charlse Cobb and Paul Douglass in 1928 which shows that to every input (Labor and Capital) there would be corresponding output. This informed the model was used to drive the model for this study as shown below

$$PER_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FIN_{it} + \beta_2 SES_{it} + \beta_3 REA_{it} + \beta_4 PTJOB_{it} + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Academic Performance = f (financial constraint, socio economic status, Recreation/Extracurricular Activities, Part-time Job)

This shows that students' academic performance depends on finances (in terms of students' financial structure) and other variables. Where "PER" represents students' academic performance, "FIN" captures the financial constraints of the students, "SES" is the socio-economic status, "REA" is the Recreation/Extracurricular Activities, and "PTJOB" is the part-time jobs undertaking by the students.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The items of the questionnaire were drawn from student's opinions and literatures on concept of academic performance among the university undergraduate students, hence the face and content validity of the instrument is ensured. The questionnaire employed Cronbach Alpha 0.85, 0.83 and 0.80 smethod of reliability to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The formula for a standardized cronbach alpha is presented below as;

$$\alpha = \frac{N \cdot \bar{c}}{\bar{v} + (N-1) \cdot c} \quad (4.1)$$

Where,

N is equal to the number of items,

c-bar is the average inter-item covariance among the items and;

v-bar equals the average variance

Estimation Technique

The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics, in the determination of the numbers of times than event occurs, we employed the use of frequency counts. More so, the study employed the use of simple percentage to enhance simplified means of conveying size or value. Lastly, we made use of ordinary least square (OLS) method of regression analysis to be able to capture the relationship between the dependent variable and the explanatory variables of the model. The data collected will be analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0. The data will be analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, simple percentages and inferential statistics such as regression analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The empirical results derived from the analysis done for this research work. It presents the descriptive analysis, the frequency table, standard deviation and regression result which is discusses in this study.

Demographic Characteristic of Respondents

Table 1.1 Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	84	56.0
Female	66	44.0
Total	150	100%

Table 1.1 shows that 84 (56.0%) of the respondents were male while 66 (44.0%) of them were female. This shows that majority of the respondents were male.

Table 1.2 Level of Respondents

Level	Frequency	Percent
ND I	29	19.3
ND II	68	45.3
HND I	36	24.0
HND II	17	11.3
Total	150	100.0

Table 1.2 shows that 68 (45.3%) respondents were in ND II, 36 (24.0%) were in HND I level, 29 (19.3%) were in ND I and 17 (11.3%) were in HND II. This shows that majority of the respondents were in ND II.

Nature of Respondents

Table 1.3 Nature of Study

Nature of Study	Frequency	Percent
Federal Polytechnic Ayede	75	50.0
The Polytechnic Ibadan	75	50.0
Total	150	100%

Table 1.4 shows that 75 (50.0%) were Federal Polytechnic Ayede while 75 (50.0%) were equally The Polytechnic Ibadan

Table 1.4 Monthly Income from other sources

Monthly Income from other sources	Frequency	Percent
Less than N1,000	8	5.3

N1,001 to N5,000	53	35.3
N5,001 to N10,000	26	17.3
N10,001 to N15,000	6	4.0
N15,001 to N20,000	7	4.7
N20,001 to N25,000	2	1.3
Missing	48	32.0
Total	150	100.0%

From table 1.4, it shows that 53 (35.3%) of the respondents have a monthly income of N1,001-N5,000, 26 (17.3%) have a monthly income of N5,001-N10,000, 8 (5.3%) have monthly income of less than N1,000

Table 1.5: Summary table of multiple regression analysis showing joint and independent influence of Parents Job status, father's education, mother's education, house ownership, financial constraint and recreational activities engaged in for Students (Federal Polytechnic Ayede)

Variables	β	T	P	R	R ²	F	P
ParentJob Status	1.117	3.896	.000	.617	.380	5.060	.000
FatherEducation	.530	.570	.571				
MotherEducation	.047	.311	.757				
Financial constraint	-.726	-2.100	.040				
Recreation activities	.062	.448	.656				
House Ownership	.003	.034	.973				
Income	-2.431	-3.013	.004				
ParentJob	.332	.657	.513				

Results from table 1.5 shows that Parent Job status, Father education, Mother education, financial constraint, recreational activities, house ownership, Income and Parent Job significantly predicted Academic performance of Federal Polytechnic Ayede Students [(R² = .380; F (7,74) = 5.060; p < .01)]. This infers that Parent Job status, Father education, Mother education, financial constraint, recreational activities, house ownership, Income and Parent Job jointly accounted for about 38.0% of the variance observable in academic performance of Federal Polytechnic Ayede students. Further, the independent contribution of Parent Job status, financial constraint and income were significant [(β = 1.117; t = 3.896; p < .000), (β = -.726; t = -2.100; p < .040) and (β = -2.431; t = -3.013; p < .004) respectively while mother education, father education, parent job, house ownership and recreational activities were not significant.

Table 1.6: Summary table of multiple regression analysis showing joint and independent influence of Parents Job status, father's education, mother's education, house ownership, financial constraint and recreational activities engaged (The Polytechnic Ibadan)

Variables	β	T	P	R	R ²	F	P
ParentJob Status	.110	.329	.743	.509	.259	3.342	.004

FatherEducation	-.595	-.467	.642				
MotherEducation	-.545	-2.018	.048				
Financial constraint	.845	2.107	.039				
Recreation activities	.548	2.373	.020				
House Ownership	-.038	-.221	.825				
Income	-.043	-.064	.949				

Results from table 1.6 shows that Parent Job status, Father Education, Mother Education, financial constraint, recreational activities, house ownership and Income significantly predicted Academic performance of the Polytechnic Ibadan students [(R² = .259; F (7, 74) = 3.342; p < .004)]. This infers that Parent Job status, Father education, Mother education, financial constraint, recreational activities, house ownership and Income jointly accounted for about 25.9% of the variance observable in academic performance of Polytechnic Ibadan students. Further, the independent contribution of Mother Education, financial constraint and recreational activities were significant [(β = -.545; t = -2.018; p < .048), (β = .845; t = 2.107; p < .039) and (β = .548; t = 2.373; p < .020) respectively while father education, Parent job status, house ownership, financial constraint and income were not significant.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study established that financial constraint causes poor academic performance. The findings showed that for Federal Polytechnic Ayede and the Polytechnic Ibadan students, financial constraint predicted academic performance of students. Socio-economic status of parents and guardians can go a long way to determine the type of school a student can attend. Most students in public schools are from poor financial background while parents that are wealthy often send their children to expensive private schools with good infrastructure and facilities. When parents are poor and cannot afford basic and essential needs of their children such as textbooks and other educational materials including payment of school fees, all these factors can contribute to poor academic performance among students.

Based on the findings of this research work carried out in the area of the relationship between financial constraint and academic performance, it was concluded that there are fewer factors that responsible or affect the academic performance of the regular students more than their the Polytechnic Ibadan counterparts. This implies that more factors affect the academic performance of the Polytechnic Ibadan students more than the Federal Polytechnic Ayede students.

Reasons for this are not farfetched because it is widely believe that the Polytechnic Ibadan students are or is expected to engage in meaningful jobs, hence the need to go for part time programs. On the hand, the regular students are not expected to get engaged in any work. Thus, maximum consideration is expected from the regular students when compared with their the Polytechnic Ibadan counterparts. More so, a lot of distractions are expected from the Polytechnic Ibadan students more than the Federal Polytechnic Ayede students. Hence, more factors affect the academic performances of the Polytechnic Ibadan students than the academic performances of the regular students.

Lastly, it was established that while financial constraint affects the academic performances of the regular students, the same financial constraint such as income do not affect the academic performances of the Polytechnic Ibadan students. Also, it can be said that even if at all financial constraint affect the Polytechnic Ibadan students, it affects the Federal Polytechnic Ayede students more than the Polytechnic Ibadan students

In line with our findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Government should make adequate provisions for more scholarships especially for indigent students whose parents cannot afford to send them to higher institution of learning.
- ii. Counselors should develop interest in the general welfare of students, counseling centers should be opened to handle the varying problems confronting students irrespective of age, financial status and gender.
- iii. Outstanding students should be rewarded with scholarships and financial aids so as to motivate them to study more effectively.
- iv. Parents should provide all support (financial, moral emotional) to their children irrespective of gender. This will enhance their academic performance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper was carried out by us, OLADUNNI Jeremiah Olagunju¹, ONIYIDE Adekunle Oyebola² ODEYEMI Olusola Olatunbosun³ POPOOLA Mufutau Akanmu⁴ AKANNI Ifayemi Alabi⁵ under strict measures to ensure originality of the work.

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